

In Memoriam Of Yesterday

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I've been thinking a whole lot about painting, about how (or if) it still matters in today's radically changing society. Of course it probably still does — after all, heavily invested personalities and institutions would never have it otherwise. But hey, you never know how things could so easily fall out of favor these days.

I remember in the mid 80s when times felt really slow, when the world felt like it was going to stay the way it had always been since the late 60s, when TV was the “new” technology that had been shaping and changing mainstream culture for decades. I'm not sure if it's because I grew up in a third world country in Manila, Philippines, but for sure art wasn't that mainstream at all, and painting was a fringe thing, almost irresponsible actually, for one to be doing in a struggling developing world of post martial law.

We lived in Quezon City, in the lower middle class suburb called Cubao (pronounced koo-baow, which I think also means a local species of banana BTW), in a house made out of 19th and early 20th century lumber leftovers from the carcass of ancestral homes in downtown Manila. It was also a small gallery, a studio upstairs, and an art framing business as well in the basement with a section of it that housed a whole bunch of workers. It was whatever it was for us to sustain ourselves — a bustling residential complex alongside several rows of apartments in a zoning nightmare of a neighborhood. Strangely enough, we also lived in the same community with other painters, like Alfredo Liongoren and Romulo Olazo, “former hippies of the 70s” who both had the same setup of a gallery/studio/frame shop kind of home.

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never ever buy a Toyota (but eventually did anyway right before he passed away).

Strangely enough, we also lived in the same community with other painters, like Alfredo Liongoren and Romulo Olazo, “former hippies of the 70s” who both had the same setup of a gallery/studio/frame shop kind of home. And then there was some work here and there throughout the day, my siblings and I helping out in whatever we could in my father’s studio. Art was something we just did as a part of our daily lives that wasn’t separate from everything else that we had to do — an odd sort of subculture, nestled awkwardly within the already-odd-enough broader culture of postcolonial Philippines. “Painting” was the only thing I knew at the time, in an art world that was hardly a market or industry, one that was slow and steady, and sparingly supported by proponents of “high culture”.

Dave Hickey once said that being an artist isn’t simply something we choose, but more like one that a community/society “elects”. He might have been right, but for me, at the time, it felt like it was a fate harshly imposed upon us whether we liked it or not. Like it was all “elect” and zero “choice”. Modern society teaches us that we are free to choose who we want to be, which is why for many years, I have tried to fight off and steer clear of this “cultural baggage” we’ve inherited that we’ve sometimes called “identity”. Yet here I am, thrust into the world some thirty-odd years later, different yet the same.

The hills are shadows, and they flow
From form to form, and nothing stands;
They melt like mist, the solid lands,
Like clouds they shape themselves and go.
But in my spirit will I dwell,

And dream my dream, and hold it true;

For tho' my lips may breathe adieu,

I cannot think the thing farewell.

— Alfred Lord Tennyson, In Memoriam, Section CXXIII